

A Different Perspective on Competitor Analysis: Examining Resource Similarities in the Framework of Airline Competitive Dynamics

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Fleet structure Airline operations Resource similarity Competitive dynamics</p> <p>Received: 29 May 2025 Revised: 19 July 2025 Accepted: 25 July 2025</p>	<p>In order to contribute to the analysis of competitive strategies in the airline transportation sector, this study examines the resource similarity levels of enterprises through their fleet structures. In addition to the direct fleet similarity measures frequently used in the literature, this study also applies a clustered fleet similarity approach based on range and seat capacity criteria. As a result of the analysis based on the fleet data of airlines operating in Turkey between 2022 and 2024, it is observed that there are significant deviations in the source similarity scores when different measurement techniques are used. In addition, a significant asymmetry in resource structures between some carrier pairs was detected. This suggests that strategic competitive positioning in the industry should be evaluated not only on the basis of aircraft type, but also on operational capabilities and fleet flexibility. The study aims to contribute to future empirical research both methodologically and theoretically by drawing attention to the need to analyze the competitive dynamics of airlines with a more holistic approach.</p>

1. Introduction

Under increasing competitive pressure on a global scale, firms' efforts to achieve sustainable competitive advantage require not only the efficient use of internal resources but also an understanding of strategic interactions with external competitors. In this context, the competitive dynamics approach has gained an important place in the literature since the 1990s to explain the nature of inter-firm competition. This approach examines the interaction processes shaped by firms' strategic moves against each other and their responses to these moves (Smith, Ferrier & Ndofor, 2001).

Resource-Based View (RBV), one of the theoretical foundations of the approach, argues that firms achieve sustainable competitive advantages through their unique resources and competencies. Chen (1996), by focusing on the concepts of market commonality and resource similarity in the analysis of inter-firm competition, argued that awareness, motivation and capability are decisive in understanding competitive

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Cite this article: Akçay, G., Karaman, D. & Yılmaz, H. B. (2025). A Different Perspective on Competitor Analysis: Examining Resource Similarities in the Framework of Airline Competitive Dynamics. *Research in Aviation Management*, 5(1), 13-30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16629070>

behavior. In particular, the fact that firms with similar resources exhibit similar strategic reflexes directly affects the structure of competitive interactions (Chen & Miller, 2012).

To explain the multi-dimensional nature of competition, Mintzberg et al. (1998) highlighted schools of strategic management that analyze strategy formulation processes through different intellectual traditions. This framework, which consists of ten schools: design, planning, positioning, entrepreneurship, cognitivism, learning, power, culture, environment and formation, emphasizes that strategies are not only rational but also dynamic, political and context-sensitive. This perspective requires that firms' competitive behaviors should be evaluated not only on economic grounds but also in terms of internal organizational structure, cultural norms and environmental stimuli. Sarvan et al. (2003) comprehensively evaluated these strategy schools and emphasized the unifying feature of the formation school over all other approaches. The study emphasized that strategies are often restructured due to unexpected situations that "disrupt the flow" and that these situations force businesses to change. This perspective suggests that the competitive dynamics of firms should be explained not only by their existing resource structure but also by the extent to which they can adapt to environmental variables. Therefore, this theoretical integrity transforms the evaluation of resource similarity through different forms of analysis in this study from a mere methodological discussion into an effort to contribute to the multidimensional nature of strategic thinking.

Empirical studies based on Chen's (1996) model also demonstrate the practical application of this theoretical framework. For example, Yaşar's (2017) research on the Ankara-Istanbul transportation line reveals that the level of awareness between transportation modes directly affects competitor identification and strategic responses. Similarly, Prince (2019) examines the relationship between resource similarity and high-performance business systems and finds that firms with similar resource structures show certain patterns in their strategic responses. Chen et al. (2020) analyze the effects of resource similarity and commitment on firm performance and provide important findings on the direction and intensity of competition.

This theoretical and empirical background shows that competition in the airline sector is shaped not only by exogenous factors but also by endogenous sources such as fleet structure. When the historical development of the Turkish civil aviation sector is examined, periodic transformations such as the state monopoly structure between 1923-1983, privatization and the search for competition after 1983, the proliferation of low-cost carriers as of 2003 and the pandemic-induced pause in 2020 stand out. As of 2023, the sector is restructuring in areas such as digitalization, sustainability and customer experience (Yaşar & Gerede, 2023).

In light of these developments, it has become an important research topic to examine which resource structures the competitive strategies of airlines operating in Turkey are based on and how these structures create a competitive environment through the level of similarity between firms. Fleet structure, one of the main determinants of competition, shapes not only service capacity but also operational flexibility and strategic mobility (Pinchemel et al, 2020). Therefore, accurately analyzing the similarity level of airline fleets will contribute to a better understanding of sectoral competition.

At this point, the main purpose of this study is to reveal whether different methods of resource similarity analysis lead to significant differences. In the study, the resource similarity in the fleet structures of airline companies is analyzed through both direct model (based on aircraft type) and clustered model (operational groupings such as range and capacity), and the effect of method differences on the results is examined comparatively.

Accordingly, the main research question of the study is stated as follows:

"Does analyzing airlines' fleets in different ways differentiate the resource similarity between airlines?"

In this context, the resource overlaps between airline companies, the degree of mutual similarity and the differences according to the types of analysis are analyzed comparatively. Thus, it is aimed to provide a methodological evaluation of whether the different methods used in resource similarity analysis create a significant difference on the results.

In light of this information, the study aims to conduct a competitive analysis based on resource similarity analysis among airline companies operating in Turkey. Within the scope of the study, the fleet structures of

the airline companies for the three-year period between 2022-2024 were analyzed and comparative analyses were carried out based on the data of this period. In the first resource similarity analysis, a comparison was made by taking into account all aircraft in the fleet of each airline. In the second analysis, a source similarity assessment was made by classifying these aircraft on the basis of operational characteristics such as type, range and capacity.

The rest of the study is organized as follows. The second section includes the literature review. In this context, the ways of using resources in the researches conducted were analyzed. The methodology section is included in the third chapter. In this section, the data and the analysis techniques used are explained in detail. The fourth section presents the findings, followed by conclusions and recommendations.

2. Theoretical Background

Porter (1980) systematically explained the methods that firms can use to analyze their industries and competitors. Basic strategy tools such as the five forces model, value chain analysis and competitive positioning strategies are detailed. These analyses contribute to the development of conscious and effective strategies in a competitive environment. Porter (1985) discussed how firms can apply cost leadership, differentiation and focus strategies to gain competitive advantage. Within the framework of the value chain, it is emphasized that the potential for value creation in each field of activity should be evaluated.

Studies aimed at understanding the nature of competition in the airline industry have been widely cited in the strategic management literature. Bailey and Liu (1995) examine the effects of mergers and consolidations in the airline industry on consumer welfare, revealing the bidirectional effects of these processes on prices, service quality and competitive dynamics. The authors argue that mergers can lead to more efficient use of resources through economies of scale; however, market concentration can have negative consequences by limiting competition. Chen and Hambrick (1995) comparatively examine the competitive behavior of small and large firms and show that small firms tend to make faster, more covert and more selective moves, while large firms respond more slowly and more visibly. These findings reveal that competitive strategies differ according to the size and configuration of business resources and support how the resource-based approach shapes competitive behavior.

Chen's (1996) work provides an important theoretical contribution to understanding the dynamic nature of inter-firm competition. By developing the "Awareness-Motivation-Capability" (AMC) model, Chen addressed how firms shape their competitive strategies and react to competitors' moves. Gimeno and Woo (1996) emphasize the potential of inter-firm strategic similarity and multimarket contacts to reduce excessive competition in multimarket environments. In this framework, they argue that firms with similar resource structures can reduce the intensity of competition and that resource homogeneity drives strategic interactions. Granstrand et al. (1997) emphasize the "disaggregated" competencies of technology-oriented multidisciplinary firms, arguing that competitive advantage does not stem from a specific core competence, but from a structure of capabilities and resources distributed across different business areas. This approach suggests that competition is not only a process of reacting to the external environment, but also a process that is proactively managed by internal capacity.

Young et al. (2000) analyzed the interaction between multi-market contact and resource differentiation and showed that firms that face competitors in multiple markets react faster but less frequently. Firms whose resources are different from their competitors adopt more aggressive strategies. These findings suggest that dynamic competition is closely related to firm resources. Peteraf and Bergen (2003) propose a multidimensional framework for strategic decision-making by integrating market-based and resource-based approaches to analyze dynamic competitive environments. According to this approach, firms should develop competitive strategies by considering not only their competitors in the external environment but also their own resource and capability structures.

Doganis (2009), while analyzing the structural conditions in the field of airline economics and marketing, discusses how businesses optimize their resource structures, especially within the framework of cost and

pricing strategies. It is emphasized that factors such as service quality, efficiency and brand positioning play a decisive role in achieving sustainable competitive advantage in an environment of intense competition. Gündüz and Semerciöz (2012) and Gündüz (2013) argue that competitive tension plays a decisive role in firms' orientation towards strategic innovation. In these studies, competitive tension is considered not only as a threat but also as a factor that encourages the restructuring of resources and the development of innovative strategies. In this framework, the interaction between external competitive conditions and internal resource structure creates a dynamic innovation environment.

Chen and Miller (2012, 2015) argue for a more comprehensive analysis of competitive dynamics and propose multidimensional frameworks that include dimensions such as timing, predictability, level of aggressiveness, and competitor profile. Emphasizing that competition is not limited to responding to competitor actions, but is directly related to firms' strategic intentions and resource capacities, these studies show that resource-based competencies play a central role in firms' proactive strategy development. Belobaba et al. (2015) examine the airline industry on a global scale, focusing on its historical development, economic structure and regulatory environment. The study provides a detailed account of how airlines use resource structures (e.g. fleet structure, operational efficiency, cost management) to determine their competitive position, thus linking the multi-layered nature of industry competition to resource-based analysis.

Hanson et al. (2017) examines how firms structure their internal resources through environmental analysis in the strategic management process and which strategies they apply to gain competitive advantage in global markets. The study emphasizes the applied aspects of strategic management concepts and reveals that resource and capability development is a key determinant of competition. Yazgan and Yiğit (2017) analyze the international competitiveness of the Turkish civil aviation sector within the framework of factors such as infrastructure, human resources, service quality and technology; and evaluate the competitive position of actors in the sector through resource structures. In this context, the study supports the relationship between resource-based analysis and sectoral competitiveness with empirical data.

Chen et al. (2020) examine how parent-subsidiary resource linkages affect the performance of the parent firm in terms of resource similarity and resource commitment. Resource similarity is determined by whether the parent and subsidiary firms have the same two-digit standard industrial classification code. Secondary data has been collected from the Taiwan institute of research economics and the Taiwan economic journal. 199 firms and 806 firm-year observations (2001-2007) are covered. The results show that resource similarity has a U-shaped relationship with parent firm performance, while resource commitment has an inverted U-shaped relationship with parent firm performance. The study has an important theoretical and managerial place in the literature for international business management.

Yaşar and Gerede (2020) examined the effect of market commonality and resource similarity on the perception of competition among firms operating in the Turkish domestic airline market. The study reveals that competition among firms is not symmetric and the perceived competitive tension varies depending on the market and resource structure. The study also emphasizes the role of non-price factors such as service variety, on-time flights and customer loyalty in achieving competitive advantage; in this respect, the study combines dynamic competition and resource-based approaches.

Sönmez and Eroğlu (2021) examine the competitive moves implemented in the Turkish airline industry and classify these moves under categories such as marketing, service, cooperation and capacity. Stating that high competitive pressure drives the industry, the study reveals how strategies change over time and shows that firms shape their competitive actions according to their resource structure.

3. Methodology

Secondary data sources were used in the research. Accordingly, the Annual Reports of the Directorate General of Civil Aviation were utilized. The number of aircraft owned by airline companies was obtained on the basis of aircraft type for each year from the relevant reports. The fleet information of airline operators was transferred to tables specific to aircraft types.

Fleet information in this study was analyzed based on the formula in Chen's (1996) "Competitor Analysis and Interfirm Rivalry". The relevant formula is as follows.

$$S_{ij} = \sum_{m=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{A_{im}}{A_i} \right) \left(\frac{A_{jm}}{A_m} \right) \right] \tag{1}$$

S_{ij} : the degree of resource similarity between airline i and airline j

A_{im} : Number of aircraft of type m owned by airline i

A_i : the total number of aircraft owned by airline i

A_{jm} : Number of aircraft type m owned by airline j

A_m : Total number of aircraft of type m in all airlines

During the fleet classification process, a new formula was created by adopting a different approach from Chen's method and classifying the aircraft based on operational characteristics such as range and seat capacity, rather than individual aircraft types (Yaşar and Gerege, 2025). The formula in question is as follows:

$$KFS_{ij} = \sum_{p=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{A_{ip}}{A_i} \right) \left(\frac{A_{jp}}{A_p} \right) \right] \tag{2}$$

KFS_{ij} : Degree of cluster fleet resource similarity between airline i and airline j

A_{ip} : Number of aircraft with p characteristics owned by airline i

A_i : the total number of aircraft owned by airline i

A_{jp} : Number of aircraft with p characteristics owned by airline j

A_p : Total number of aircraft with p characteristics in all airlines

In this context, two separate data sets were created. Analyses based on aircraft types are defined as "Direct Fleet", while analyses based on range and seat capacity are called "Cluster Fleet". For the years 2022, 2023 and 2024, source similarity analyses were conducted using both data sets and the differences between these years were evaluated comparatively. In this direction, firstly, Table 1 shows the aircraft and grouping criteria.

Table 1. Grouping of Aircraft

Airplane Model Groups	Grouping Criteria
A320, B738, B738M, B737M	Short-medium range, 150-180 seats
A321, B739, B739M	Narrow body, 200+ seats
A350, B787 (B789)	Wide body, long range
A330	Wide body, medium/long range
B773ER	Very long range, high capacity
A319	Narrow body, short range

One of the most important factors shaping the competitive strategies of airline companies is their fleet structure. Classification of aircraft models according to range, capacity and airframe type plays a critical role in fleet planning. The narrow-body and short-range A319 enables effective management of regional markets and increases competitiveness in markets with low demand intensity (Özdemir et al., 2011). A320, B738, B738M and B737M models, which are medium-range and have a seat capacity of approximately 150-180 seats, offer operational efficiency for short and medium-haul routes, while aircraft with a seat capacity of

over 200, such as A321, B739 and B739M, provide airlines with a competitive advantage on high-demand routes (Kiracı & Bakır, 2018). The wide-body and long-range A350 and B787 (B789) models contribute to network expansion strategies, especially in the international market, while aircraft compatible with both medium and long-range flights, such as the A330, provide operational flexibility to fleets (Ongan, 2007). The very long-range and high-capacity B773ER model provides a competitive advantage on intercontinental high-traffic routes (Sun et al., 2011). This diversity provides airlines with strategic advantages in terms of both cost management and market diversification.

4. Findings

This section presents the research findings. In this context, firstly, the number of aircraft in the fleets of airline companies will be given in tables, and then the tables regarding the fleets re-evaluated according to their characteristics within the scope of the research will be presented. Finally, source similarity analyses will be presented in tables after using the formula commonly used in the literature and the formula recreated by the authors within the scope of the research. In this context, firstly, Table 2 provides information on the fleets of airline companies for the year 2022.

Table 2 . 2022 Airline Aircraft Fleet Information

	A319	A320	A321	A330	A350	B738	B738M	B739M	B739ER	B773ER	B789	Airline Total
THY	6	14	108	50	11	79	27	5	15	33	15	363
PGT		53	25			18						96
SXS						53	9					62
CAI						14	6					20
STW			1	2								3
FHY		10										10
TWI							5					5
BBN												0
MGA						3				1		4
ANKA				2								2
Aircraft Type Total	6	77	134	54	11	167	47	5	15	33	15	565

According to the information in Table 2, Turkish Airlines has 363 aircraft, of which 189 are Airbus and 174 are Boeing. Of these aircraft, 109 are wide-body and 254 are narrow-body. When analyzed by type, THY fleet consists of 6 A319s, 14 A320s, 108 A321s, 50 A330s and 11 A350s. On the other hand, there are 79 B738s, 27 B738Ms, 5 B739Ms, 15 B739ERs, 33 B777ERs and 15 B789s.

Pegasus has a total of 96 aircraft, 78 of which are Airbus and 18 of which are Boeing aircraft. All of these aircraft are narrow-body. The fleet consists of 53 A320, 25 A321 and 18 B738 aircraft. SunExpress has 62 aircraft in total, all of which are narrow-body Boeing aircraft. Of these 62 aircraft, 53 are B738s and 9 are B738Ms. Corendon Airlines has 20 aircraft (14 B738-6 B738M), all of which are narrow-body Boeing aircraft.

Southwind Airlines has a total of 3 aircraft, all of which are Airbus models. Of these aircraft, 1 is narrow body (A321) and 2 is wide body (A 330). FreeBird has a total of 10 aircraft in its fleet, all of which are narrow-body A320s. Tailwind's total number of aircraft is 5, all of which are narrow-body Boeing models. BBN Airlines has no aircraft in its fleet as of 2022. Mavi Gök Airlines has 4 aircraft, all of which are Boeing models. 3 of them are narrow body (B738) and 1 wide body (B777ER) aircraft. Air Anka has 2 aircraft, all of which are wide-body Airbus models.

The total number of aircraft in all fleets is 565, of which 282 are Airbus and 283 are Boeing. Of these aircraft, 113 are wide-body and 452 are narrow-body. The fleet consists of 6 A319s, 77 A320s, 134 A321s, 54 A330s, 11 A350s, 167 B738s, 47 B738Ms, 5 B739Ms, 15 B739ERs, 33 B777ERs and 15 B789s.

Turkish Airlines has the most airplanes and Air Anka has the fewest. BBN Airlines has no aircraft yet, as its establishment year is 2022. Turkish Airlines has the most Airbus models with 189 and the most Boeing models with 174. The airline with the least number of Airbus is Air Anka with 2 units and the airline with the least number of Boeing models is Mavi Gök Airlines with 1 unit. Turkish Airlines has the most wide-body airlines and the most narrow-body airlines. Mavi Gök Airlines has the least number of wide-body airlines with 1. The airline with the least number of narrow body is Southwind Airlines with 1. Following the 2022 airline fleet information, Table 3 shows the airline fleet information for 2023.

Table 3 . 2023 Airline Aircraft Fleets

	A319	A320	A321	A330	A350	B738	B738M	B739M	B739ER	B773ER	B789	Airline Total
THY	6	21	121	49	16	85	27	5	15	35	22	402
PGT		52	41			16						109
SXS						50	12					62
CAI						12	7					19
STW			3	2			3			4		12
FHY		10										10
TWI							7					7
BBN		1	4									5
MGA						2			2	1		5
ANKA	1			2								3
Aircraft Type Total	7	84	169	53	16	165	56	5	17	40	22	634

According to 2023 data, it was observed that the total number of aircraft of operating airline companies increased by 69 units to 634 compared to the previous year. The main reasons for the increase include the weakening of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, the increase in demand for air transportation, and the acceleration of restructuring and fleet development steps in the aviation sector (Semercioğlu and Özkoç, 2021).

In 2023, Turkish Airlines added 39 new aircraft to its fleet, bringing the total number of aircraft to 402. Accordingly, the number of Airbus and Boeing aircraft reached 213 and 189, respectively. The number of wide-body and narrow-body aircraft in Turkish Airlines' fleet reached 280 and 122, respectively. These data show that the company continues to grow in both long-haul and short- and medium-haul routes (Turkish Airlines, 2023).

Pegasus Airlines added 13 aircraft to its fleet, reaching a total of 109 aircraft. Of these, 93 are Airbus and 16 are Boeing aircraft, all of which are narrow-body. Pegasus' focus on narrow-body aircraft indicates that it prefers flights with faster turnaround times and short-haul routes due to its low-cost airline model (Pegasus Hava Taşımacılığı A. Ş., 2023). SunExpress did not add any new aircraft to its fleet in the relevant period. The company maintained its narrow body fleet, reflecting its specialization in touristic and charter flights (SunExpress, (n.d.)).

Corendon Airlines' fleet decreased by 1 aircraft to 19 aircraft. When analyzed by type, while there were 6 B738Ms in 2022, this number increased to 7 in 2023. When the fleet data of Southwind Airlines in 2022 and 2023 are analyzed, it is seen that the company has gone through a serious fleet expansion. The fleet, which consisted of only 3 aircraft in 2022, increased to a total of 12 aircraft in 2023. The number of A321 narrow-body aircraft was increased from 1 to 3, increasing the capacity on short and medium range routes. While the number of A330 wide-body aircraft remained constant, the addition of 3 Boeing 738M (narrow-body) and 4 Boeing 773ER (wide-body) aircraft to the fleet shows that the airline aims to increase its efficiency on both short-medium range and long-range flights. This fleet expansion shows that Southwind Airlines has adopted a growth-oriented fleet strategy and aims to serve more routes by increasing its operational capacity.

Freebird Airlines kept its fleet unchanged with 10 aircraft. When Tailwind Airlines' 2023 data is analyzed, it is seen that the number of Boeing 738M type aircraft has increased. The number of aircraft type increased from 5 in 2022 to 7 in 2023. When the fleet structure of Mavi Gök Airlines for 2023 is analyzed, a differentiation is observed in the fleet. Having 3 B738 and 1 B773ER aircraft in 2022, the company reduced the number of B738s to 2 in 2023, while adding 2 B739ERs to the fleet and keeping the number of B773ERs constant. This can be considered as a move towards the company's goal of diversifying the fleet and increasing operational efficiency by opting for aircraft with higher capacity and range.

In 2022, Air Anka had only 2 A330s in its fleet, increasing this number to 3 in 2023. This increase reflects the company's intention to focus on its strategy of maintaining long-haul or charter operations. BBN Airlines, on the other hand, started to build its fleet with 5 aircraft in 2023, while it did not have any aircraft in 2022. This move indicates the entry of a new player into the sector and the enrichment and strengthening of competitive dynamics.

In 2023, the total number of aircrafts operated by airline companies was 634. Of these aircraft, 313 are Airbus and 321 are Boeing type aircraft. When analyzed by fuselage type, the majority of the aircraft are narrow-bodied and there are 503 narrow-bodied aircraft in total. On the other hand, there are 131 wide-body aircraft. The most common Airbus model is A321 with 169 units, followed by A320 with 84 units and wide-body A330 with 53 units. Among Boeing models, the B738 stands out with 165 units, followed by 56 B738Ms and 40 B773ERs. Following the 2023 airline fleet data, Table 4 shows the airline fleet data for 2024.

Table 4 . 2024 Airline Aircraft Fleets

	A319	A320	A321	A330	A350	B738	B738M	B739M	B739ER	B773ER	B789	Airline Total
THY	6	30	133	49	24	74	27	5	15	36	23	422
PGT		52	57			10						119
SXS						55	17					72
CAI						9	6					15
STW			3	2			3			4		12
FHY		11										11
TWI						7						7
BBN		2	5									7
MGA						8			2	1		11
ANKA				3								3
Aircraft Type Total	6	95	198	54	24	163	53	5	17	41	23	679

According to 2024 data, the total number of aircraft of Turkish Airlines is 422. Of these, 242 are Airbus and 180 are Boeing. Of these aircraft, 132 are wide-body and 290 are narrow-body. When analyzed by type, THY fleet consists of 6 A319s, 30 A320s, 49 A330s, 133 A321s and 24 A350s. On the other hand, there are 74 B738s, 27 B738Ms, 5 B739Ms, 15 B739ERs, 36 B777ERs and 23 B789s.

Pegasus has a total of 119 aircraft, 109 of which are Airbus and 10 of which are Boeing aircraft. All of these aircraft are narrow-body. The fleet consists of 52 A320, 57 A321 and 10 B738 aircraft. SunExpress has 72 aircraft in total, all of which are narrow-body Boeing models. Of these 72 aircraft, 55 are B738 and 17 are B738M. Corendon Airlines has a total number of 72 aircraft, all of which are narrow-body Boeing aircraft. In terms of type, 55 of the aircraft are B738 and 17 are B738M models.

Southwind Airlines has a total of 12 aircraft in its fleet, 5 of which are Airbus and 7 Boeing. According to the aircraft in the fleet; There are 3 of the A321 model and 2 of the A330 model. Boeing fleet consists of B738M (3 units) and B777ER (4 units) models. FreeBird has a total of 11 aircraft, all of which are narrow-body A320 models of Airbus. Tailwind's total number of aircraft is 7 aircraft (B738M), all narrow-body. BBN Airlines has 7 narrow-body A320 (2) - A321 (5) aircraft. Blue Sky Airlines has a total of 11 aircraft, of which 1 is wide body

and 10 are narrow body. Among these, there are 8 of B738, 2 of B739ER and 1 of B773ER. Air Anka has 3 wide-body Airbus A330 aircraft.

According to 2024 data, the total number of aircraft in all fleets increased by 45 aircraft compared to 2023, reaching 679. Of these, 302 are Airbus and 377 are Boeing aircraft. When the aircraft in the fleet are analyzed according to their airframe structure, it is seen that narrow-body aircraft are much more common than wide-body aircraft. According to the aircraft types, it is observed that the most used Airbus aircraft is A321 with 198 units, while Boeing's B738 model is the most preferred with 163 units.

According to 2024 data, Turkish Airlines has the most aircraft with 422 aircraft, while Air Anka has the fewest with 3 aircraft. THY has the highest number of both aircraft models with 242 Airbus and 180 Boeing. Air Anka has the least number of Airbus with 3 aircraft, while Tailwind and Southwind Airlines have the least number of Boeing aircraft with 7 aircraft each. Looking at the changes in the fleet, THY added 20 aircraft, Pegasus and SunExpress 10 each, FreeBird 1, BBN Airlines 2 and Mavi Gök Airlines 6. The fleet numbers of Southwind Airlines and Tailwind remained unchanged. Corendon Airlines, on the other hand, decreased 4 aircraft from its fleet. 3 of them are B738 and 1 of them is B738M model.

Following the 2022-2024 fleet information of airline operators, converted fleet information, in which aircraft types with similar characteristics are grouped and analyzed, will be presented. In this context, converted fleet information for 2022 is presented in Table 5.

Table 5 . 2022 Converted Fleet Information

	A319	A320/B738/B737M	A321/B739/B739M	A350/B787	A330	B773	Airline Total
THY	6	120	128	26	50	33	363
PGT	0	71	25	0	0	0	96
SXS	0	62	0	0	0	0	62
CAI	0	20	0	0	0	0	20
STW	0	0	1	0	2	0	3
FHY	0	10	0	0	0	0	10
TWI	0	5	0	0	0	0	5
BBN							0
MGA	0	3	0	0	0	1	4
ANKA	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
Aircraft Type Total	6	291	154	26	54	34	565

In Table 5, the aircraft in the fleet of airline companies are grouped according to their range and seat capacity. Accordingly, Turkish Airlines' aircraft are categorized into two main groups. The first group includes B737 and A320 series airplanes, which are widely used in short and medium distances. The other group consists of B739 and A321 aircraft, which are the versions of B737 and A320 with higher seat capacities. These two groups account for 68% of the total fleet. The same is true for Pegasus. The aircraft are grouped in two main groups, just like THY, and this covers the entire fleet. Sun Express and Corendon have a single group. It is noteworthy that airlines like SunExpress and Corendon are concentrated in the A320/B738 group, while a small-scale airline like Air Anka has only wide-body A330 aircraft. Variants of the B737 are included in this group. Following the 2022 converted fleet information, Table 6 shows the 2023 converted fleet information.

Table 6 . 2023 Converted Fleet Information

	A319	A320/B738/B737M	A321/B739/B739M	A350/B787	A330	B773	Airline Total
THY	6	133	141	38	49	35	402
PGT	0	68	41	0	0	0	109

SXS	0	62	0	0	0	0	62
CAI	0	19	0	0	0	0	19
STW	0	3	3	0	2	4	12
FHY	0	10	0	0	0	0	10
TWI	0	7	0	0	0	0	7
BBN	0	1	4	0	0	0	5
MGA	0	2	2	0	0	1	5
ANKA	1	0	0	0	2	0	3
Aircraft Type Total	7	305	191	38	53	40	634

In the table above, the aircraft in the fleet of the airlines mentioned in the converted fleet information as of 2023 are classified according to their range and seat capacity. According to the information in the table, the aircraft in the Turkish Airlines fleet are again divided into two main groups. The first group includes short- and medium-range aircraft, while the second group includes wide-body and long-range aircraft. THY has a total of 402 aircraft in its fleet and the majority of the fleet consists of A321, B738 and B739M aircraft. Similarly, Pegasus Airlines' fleet was divided into two main groups and continued to operate with a total of 109 aircraft. Sun Express, on the other hand, has a fleet of only one group and consists of a total of 62 aircraft. Corendon, on the other hand, concentrated on the A320/B738 group with a fleet of 19 aircraft. According to the data in the table, Air Anka added 1 A319 model to its fleet in addition to 2022, while continuing to use wide-body A330 aircraft. On the other hand, some small-scale companies have seen small increases in the number of aircraft. Since the number of aircraft of small-scale airlines is relatively very low, details regarding the grouping are not included. Following the 2023 converted fleet information, Table 7 presents the 2024 converted fleet information.

Table 7 . 2024 Converted Fleet Information

	A319	A320/B738/B737M	A321/B739/B739M	A350/B787	A330	B773	Airline Total
THY	6	131	153	47	49	36	422
PGT	0	62	57	0	0	0	119
SXS	0	72	0	0	0	0	72
CAI	0	15	0	0	0	0	15
STW	0	3	3	0	2	4	12
FHY	0	11	0	0	0	0	11
TWI	0	7	0	0	0	0	7
BBN	0	2	5	0	0	0	7
MGA	0	8	2	0	0	1	11
ANKA	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
Aircraft Type Total	6	311	220	47	54	41	679

The table presents the converted fleet information of airlines as of 2024. Again, two main groups constitute the majority of THY's fleet. A321, B738 and B739M aircraft, which are short and medium range aircraft, represent a significant portion of this fleet. Just like THY, Pegasus fleet is also divided into two main groups and these groups cover the entire fleet. SunExpress fleet, on the other hand, showed a remarkable increase to 72 aircraft. All of this fleet is organized in the A320/B738 group. The fleets of Corendon, Freebird and Tailwind airlines are grouped in a single group and consist of short-medium range A320/B738 aircraft. Air Anka maintained its structure consisting only of wide-body A330 aircraft and continued its operations with 3 aircraft. Overall, the fleet of all airline operators grew significantly, reaching 679 aircraft.

For the years 2022, 2023 and 2024, source similarity analyses were performed with both original (ungrouped) fleet data and grouped fleet data. Original fleet data will be referred to as direct fleet (DF) and grouped fleet data will be referred to as cluster fleet (CF). In this context, firstly, Table 8 shows the DF data for 2022.

Table 8 . 2022 DF Resource Similarity Matrix

	THY	PGT	SXS	CAI	STW	FHY	TWI	BBN	MGA	ANKA
THY		0,105	0,083	0,027	0,007	0,005	0,007		0,006	0,005
PGT	0,398		0,059	0,015	0,001	0,071			0,003	
SXS	0,487	0,092		0,090			0,015		0,015	
CAI	0,503	0,075	0,279				0,031		0,012	
STW	0,885	0,062								0,024
FHY	0,181	0,688								
TWI	0,574		0,191	0,127						
BBN										
MGA	0,604	0,080	0,238	0,062						
ANKA	0,925				0,037					

According to the information provided in Table 8, there is no similarity between some airlines in terms of resources at all. In 2022, Air Anka's resources have less overlap with other airlines and only Turkish Airlines and Southwind airlines have similar resources ($DFRS_{ANKA-THY} = 0.925$; $DFRS_{ANKA-STW} = 0.037$). THY has the most resource overlap with PGT ($DFRS_{THY-PGT} = 0.105$). In addition, the airline with the least source overlap is FHY ($DFRS_{THY-FHY} = 0.005$). From the FHY perspective, there is resource overlap with only 2 airlines. These airlines are PGT ($DFRS_{FHY-PGT} = 0.688$) and THY ($DFRS_{FHY-THY} = 0.181$). On the other hand, PGT does not have a high level of source similarity with FHY ($DFRS_{PGT-FHY} = 0.071$). PGT has the highest source overlap with THY ($DFRS_{PGT-THY} = 0.398$), while the lowest source overlap is with MGA ($DFRS_{PGT-MGA} = 0.003$).

In addition to this information, there are airlines with no source overlap at all. For example, competitor pairs such as STW-TWI, ANKA-PGT, SXS-FHY, FHY-CAI have no source overlap. STW has the least source overlap with ANKA ($DFRS_{STW-ANKA} = 0.024$). TWI has resource overlap with only 3 airlines. These are THY, SXS, CAI ($DFRS_{TWI-THY} = 0.574$; $DFRS_{TWI-SXS} = 0.191$; $DFRS_{TWI-CAI} = 0.127$) respectively. As a general assessment, THY has resource overlap with every airline due to its high resource diversity. On the other hand, ANKA and FHY have resource overlaps with only two airlines each. BBN, on the other hand, does not have any overlap since it does not yet have an aircraft in its fleet as of 2022.

An analysis of competitor pairs reveals that many competitor pairs exhibit asymmetries in terms of resource similarity. For example, the resource similarity between THY-PGT is 0.105, while PGT-THY is 0.398. In this sense, THY can easily respond to a move made by Pegasus, but PGT has less capability than THY in this context. There are also competitor pairs where the asymmetry is very high. For example, the degree of similarity of the resources of THY-STW is 0.007, while the corresponding value of STW-THY is 0.885. In another example, the similarity of THY-ANKA is 0.005, while ANKA-THY is 0.925. Similar comments made above for the THY-PGT pair can also be made for these two competitor pairs. Following the 2022 DFRS information, Table 9 presents the CF information for 2022.

Table 9 . 2022 CF Resource Similarity Matrix

	THY	PGT	SXS	CAI	STW	FHY	TWI	BBN	MGA	ANKA
THY		0,138	0,070	0,023	0,007	0,011	0,006		0,006	0,005
PGT	0,521		0,158	0,051	0,002	0,025	0,013		0,008	
SXS	0,412	0,244		0,069		0,034	0,017		0,010	
CAI	0,412	0,244	0,213			0,034	0,017		0,010	
STW	0,894	0,054								0,025
FHY	0,412	0,244	0,213	0,069			0,017		0,010	

TWI	0,412	0,244	0,213	0,069		0,034			0,010	
BBN										
MGA	0,552	0,183	0,160	0,052		0,026	0,013			
ANKA	0,926				0,037					

According to the information provided in the table, there is no resource overlap at all between some airlines. In 2022, THY has the highest resource overlap with PGT ($CFRS_{THY-PGT} = 0.137$) and the least resource overlap with STW ($CFRS_{THY-STW} = 0.007$). PGT has the most resource similarity with THY ($CFRS_{PGT-THY} = 0.521$) and the least with STW ($CFRS_{PGT-STW} = 0.001$). From the SXS perspective, THY is seen as the most important competitor in terms of resources ($CFRS_{SXS-THY} = 0.412$). MGA is seen as the least important competitor ($CFRS_{SXS-MGA} = 0.010$). For CAI, the highest source overlap is with THY ($CFRS_{CAI-THY} = 0.412$) and the lowest source overlap is with MGA ($CFRS_{CAI-MGA} = 0.010$).

The source similarity of STW with THY is very high ($CFRS_{STW-THY} = 0.894$) and the lowest with ANKA ($CFRS_{STW-ANKA} = 0.024$). For FHY, the highest source overlap was with THY ($CFRS_{FHY-THY} = 0.412$), while the lowest source overlap was with MGA ($CFRS_{FHY-MGA} = 0.010$). For TWI, the highest source overlap was with THY ($CFRS_{TWI-THY} = 0.412$) and the lowest source overlap was with MGA ($CFRS_{TWI-MGA} = 0.010$). MGA's competitors with the highest and lowest resource similarity are THY ($CFRS_{MGA-THY} = 0.551$) and TWI ($CFRS_{MGA-TWI} = 0.012$). Finally, ANKA has the most resource similarity with THY ($CFRS_{ANKA-THY} = 0.925$) and the least with STW ($CFRS_{ANKA-STW} = 0.037$).

When we look at the evaluations on the basis of competitor pairs, it is seen that there is asymmetry in terms of resource similarity in many competitor pairs on the basis of CF as in DF. While the situation does not change much in rival pairs such as THY-ANKA, THY-STW where the asymmetry is very high, it is seen that the asymmetry increases in the THY-PGT rival pair. In some competitor pairs, it is seen that the amount of asymmetry decreases according to the analysis with DF.

For the year 2022, when the resource similarities between airlines are compared in terms of Direct Fleet (DF) information and Cluster Fleet (CF) information, it is seen that while a total of 38 competitor pairs were identified as competitors in terms of resource similarity in the analysis conducted with DF, this number increased to 50 in the CF table where similar aircraft are grouped. This shows that the similarities are revealed in a more comprehensive manner thanks to the detailed grouping. When the competitor pairs are analyzed individually in terms of resource similarity, it is seen that the resource similarity values of 40 competitor pairs have increased in the analyses made with CF, while this number has decreased in 10 competitor pairs. Following the 2022 evaluations, Table 10 presents the DF resource similarity matrix for 2023.

Table 10 . 2023 DF Resource Similarity Matrix

	THY	PGT	SXS	CAI	STW	FHY	TWI	BBN	MGA	ANKA
THY		0,126	0,078	0,024	0,022	0,006	0,008	0,008	0,009	0,007
PGT	0,464		0,044	0,011	0,007	0,057		0,015	0,002	
SXS	0,509	0,078		0,083	0,010		0,024		0,010	
CAI	0,503	0,061	0,270		0,020		0,046		0,008	
STW	0,745	0,061	0,054	0,031			0,031	0,006	0,008	0,006
FHY	0,250	0,619						0,012		
TWI	0,482		0,214	0,125	0,054					
BBN	0,623	0,318			0,014	0,024				
MGA	0,734	0,039	0,121	0,029	0,020					
ANKA	0,902				0,025					

According to the information in Table 10, there is no similarity between some airlines in terms of resources. One of the rival pairs with the highest resource similarity is THY and STW ($DFRS_{THY-STW} = 0.745$) and the other

is THY and MGA ($DFRS_{THY-MGA} = 0.734$). However, it is noteworthy that CAI shows a significant similarity only with SXS (0.2703), while it has a low level of association with other airlines.

According to 2023 data, Air Anka's resources are most similar to Turkish Airlines ($KB_{ANKA-THY} = 0.902$). Apart from this, ANKA only has a low level of resource similarity with STW ($DFRS_{ANKA-STW} = 0.025$). Similarly, the airline with which MGA has the highest source similarity is THY ($DFRS_{(MGA-THY)} = 0.734$). The other airlines with lower source similarity are SXS ($DFRS_{MGA-SXS} = 0.121$), PGT ($DFRS_{MGA-PGT} = 0.039$), CAI ($DFRS_{MGA-CAI} = 0.029$), STW ($DFRS_{MGA-STW} = 0.020$). BBN has a significant source similarity only with THY ($DFRS_{BBN-THY} = 0.623$) and PGT ($DFRS_{BBN-PGT} = 0.318$). TWI airline stands out in source similarity with THY ($DFRS_{TWI-THY} = 0.482$), followed by SXS ($DFRS_{TWI-SXS} = 0.214$), CAI ($DFRS_{TWI-CAI} = 0.125$), STW ($DFRS_{TWI-STW} = 0.054$).

When we look at the evaluations on the basis of competitor pairs, we see that there is asymmetry in terms of resource similarity in many competitor pairs. For example, the source similarity between THY and PGT is not very high from the perspective of THY ($DFRSTHY-PGT = 0.126$), while it is high from the perspective of PGT ($DFRS_{PGT-THY} = 0.464$). The figures show that the THY-PGT competitor pair similarity increases in both directions. There are also rival pairs where the asymmetry is very high, as in 2022. For example, while the similarity of THY's sources with STW ($DFRS_{THY-STW} = 0.022$) is low, STW's source similarity with THY ($DFRS_{STW-THY} = 0.745$) is much higher. In another example, while the similarity of THY's sources with ANKA ($DFRS_{THY-ANKA} = 0.007$) is low, ANKA's source similarity with THY ($DFRS_{ANKA-THY} = 0.902$) is much higher. BBN airlines, which added its first aircraft to its fleet in 2023, has a high similarity with THY ($DFRS_{BBN-THY} = 0.623$), while this ratio is much lower for THY ($DFRS_{THY-BBN} = 0.008$). There is a high degree of asymmetry here, just like the other competitor pairs. Following the 2023 DF matrix, Table 11 presents the 2023 CF resource similarity matrix.

Table 11 . 2023 CF Resource Similarity Matrix

	THY	PGT	SXS	CAI	STW	FHY	TWI	BBN	MGA	ANKA
THY		0,149	0,067	0,021	0,022	0,011	0,008	0,008	0,008	0,007
PGT	0,550		0,127	0,039	0,012	0,020	0,014	0,010	0,008	
SXS	0,436	0,223		0,062	0,010	0,033	0,023	0,003	0,007	
CAI	0,436	0,223	0,203		0,010	0,033	0,023	0,003	0,007	
STW	0,739	0,109	0,051	0,016		0,008	0,006	0,006	0,013	0,006
FHY	0,436	0,223	0,203	0,062	0,010		0,023	0,003	0,007	
TWI	0,436	0,223	0,203	0,062	0,010	0,033		0,003	0,007	
BBN	0,678	0,216	0,041	0,012	0,015	0,007	0,005		0,010	
MGA	0,645	0,175	0,081	0,025	0,030	0,013	0,009	0,010		
ANKA	0,902				0,025					

Table 11 shows that resource similarity ratios have increased among some airlines, while there is still no significant similarity among others. As in other years, the airline with which Air Anka is most similar is THY ($CFRS_{ANKA-THY} = 0.902$). MGA also has overlapping resources with THY ($CFRS_{MGA-THY} = 0.645$) and PGT ($CFRS_{MGA-PGT} = 0.175$), but its similarity with other airlines is quite low. BBN airline has high resource similarity with THY and PGT ($CFRS_{BBN-PGT} = 0.216$). TWI exhibited significant similarities with THY ($CFRS_{TWI-THY} = 0.436$), PGT ($CFRS_{TWI-PGT} = 0.223$) and SXS ($CFRS_{TWI-SXS} = 0.203$). STW maintains a high source similarity with THY ($CFRS_{STW-THY} = 0.739$), while its similarity with other airlines is relatively low. While CAI's source similarity with SXS ($CFRS_{CAI-SXS} = 0.203$), FHY ($CFRS_{CAI-FHY} = 0.033$) and TWI ($CFRS_{CAI-TWI} = 0.023$) is observed; SXS airline overlaps most with THY ($CFRS_{SXS-THY} = 0.436$), PGT ($CFRS_{SXS-PGT} = 0.223$) and CAI ($CFRS_{SXS-CAI} = 0.062$).

According to the 2023 CFRS matrix, THY-PGT ($CFRS_{THY-PGT} = 0.149$, $CFRS_{PGT-THY} = 0.550$) shows the highest source similarity; In addition, the resource similarity of THY with ANKA ($CFRS_{THY-ANKA} = 0.007$, $CFRS_{ANKA-THY} = 0.902$), BBN ($CFRS_{THY-BBN} = 0.008$, $CFRS_{BBN-THY} = 0.678$) and MGA ($CFRS_{THY-MGA} = 0.008$, $CFRS_{MGA-THY} = 0.6445$) airlines is also noteworthy. As a result, THY's resources overlap with many airlines, while Air Anka's resources largely overlap only with THY.

Considering the evaluations on the basis of competitor pairs, it can be said that the asymmetry observed in 2022 on the basis of CF is also valid for 2023. For 2023, when the resource similarities between airlines are compared in the context of Direct Fleet (DF) information and Cluster Fleet (CF) information, it is seen that a total of 54 competitor pairs are competitors in terms of resource similarity in the analysis made with DF, while this number increases to 76 in the CF table where similar aircraft are grouped. The addition of airplanes to the fleet of BBN airline increased the amount of resource similarity overlap between the related airlines. When competitor pairs are analyzed individually in terms of resource similarity, it is seen that the resource similarity values of 44 competitor pairs increased in the analysis made with CF, while this number decreased in 32 competitor pairs. Following the 2023 CFRS information, Table 12 presents the DF information for 2024.

Table 12 . 2024 DF Source Similarity Matrix

	THY	PGT	SXS	CAI	STW	FHY	TWI	BBN	MGA	ANKA
THY		0,140	0,080	0,017	0,021	0,008	0,008	0,009	0,015	0,006
PGT	0,498		0,028	0,005	0,007	0,051	0,004	0,021	0,004	
SXS	0,467	0,047		0,069	0,013		0,033		0,037	
CAI	0,476	0,037	0,331		0,023		0,026		0,029	
STW	0,739	0,072	0,080	0,028				0,006	0,008	0,009
FHY	0,316	0,547						0,021		
TWI	0,454	0,061	0,337	0,055					0,049	
BBN	0,570	0,362			0,011	0,033				
MGA	0,570	0,045	0,245	0,040	0,009		0,031			
ANKA	0,907				0,037					

According to the data in Table 12, there is no significant similarity among airline companies in terms of resources in 2024. The general trend is that the resources of airline companies differ from each other. However, relatively higher levels of resource similarities have been identified among some airlines. According to 2024 data, THY has the highest resource similarity with PGT ($DFRS_{THY-PGT}=0.1404$) and the lowest resource similarity with ANKA ($DFRS_{THY-ANKA}=0.006451$). On the other hand, when ANKA's resource similarities are analyzed, there is resource overlap with only two companies (THY and STW) among the nine airlines. Of these two companies, ANKA's resource similarity with THY is quite high ($DFRS_{ANKA-THY}=0.907407$), while its resource similarity with STW is quite low ($DFRS_{ANKA-STW}=0.037037$). For CAI, source similarity ratios are generally low compared to the other nine companies. CAI's highest source similarity was with THY ($DFRS_{CAI-THY}=0.476166$), while the lowest source similarity was with STW ($DFRS_{CAI-STW}=0.022642$). Looking at the source similarity ratios of STW, the highest similarities were observed with THY ($DFRS_{STW-THY}=0.739205$), PGT ($DFRS_{STW-PGT}=0.07197$) and SXS ($DFRS_{STW-SXS}=0.337423$), while the lowest source similarity was found with BBN ($DFRS_{STW-BBN}=0.006313$).

BBN shows resource overlap with only four of the nine airlines. These airlines and their source similarity ratios are THY ($DFRS_{BBN-THY}=0.570024$), PGT ($DFRS_{BBN-PGT}=0.362019$), STW ($DFRS_{BBN-STW}=0.010823$) and FHY ($DFRS_{BBN-FHY}=0.033083$). FHY Airlines shows source similarity with only three of the nine companies. Among these companies, the lowest source similarity ratio is realized with BBN ($DFRS_{FHY-BBN}=0.021053$). On the other hand, the source similarity ratio of SXS to MGA ($DFRS_{SXS-MGA}=0.037491$) is average, while the source similarity ratio of MGA to SXS ($DFRS_{MGA-SXS}=0.245399$) is lower. TWI shows resource overlap with five different airlines. Among these airlines, TWI has the lowest source similarity with MGA ($DFRS_{TWI-MGA}=0.04908$). In terms of PGT Airlines, there is no source overlap only with ANKA. On the other hand, the highest source similarity was found with THY ($DFRS_{PGT-THY}=0.497889$) and the lowest source similarity was found with TWI ($DFRS_{PGT-TWI}=0.003609$).

In general, THY's resource similarity ratios are higher than the other nine airlines due to the fact that its resource structure is quite diverse. On the other hand, ANKA's more uniform resource structure resulted in a lower resource overlap compared to the other airlines. Following the 2024 DFRS information, Table 13 presents the CFRS information for 2024.

Table 13 . 2024 CF Source Similarity Matrix

	THY	PGT	SXS	CAI	STW	FHY	TWI	BBN	MGA	ANKA
THY		0,156	0,072	0,015	0,021	0,011	0,007	0,010	0,013	0,006
PGT	0,553		0,121	0,025	0,012	0,018	0,012	0,014	0,018	
SXS	0,421	0,199		0,048	0,010	0,035	0,023	0,006	0,026	
CAI	0,421	0,199	0,232		0,010	0,035	0,023	0,006	0,026	
STW	0,723	0,115	0,058	0,012		0,009	0,006	0,007	0,017	0,009
FHY	0,421	0,199	0,232	0,048	0,010		0,023	0,006	0,026	
TWI	0,421	0,199	0,232	0,048	0,010	0,035		0,006	0,026	
BBN	0,617	0,242	0,066	0,014	0,012	0,010	0,006		0,014	
MGA	0,513	0,192	0,168	0,035	0,018	0,026	0,016	0,009		
ANKA	0,907				0,037					

The table above shows the resource similarity matrix obtained by grouping according to the information provided. Accordingly, STW has a high source similarity with THY ($CFRS_{STW-THY} = 0.723$) and ANKA has almost a one-to-one overlap with THY ($CFRS_{ANKA-THY} = 0.907$). In addition, PGT's resource similarity ratio with THY is above average ($CFRS_{PGT-THY} = 0.552$), while its similarity ratio with STW is quite low ($CFRS_{PGT-STW} = 0.011$). Among all firms, CAI shows no resource overlap only with ANKA. On the other hand, the highest resource similarity is observed with THY ($CFRS_{CAI-THY} = 0.421$), SXS ($CFRS_{CAI-SXS} = 0.231$) and PGT ($CFRS_{CAI-PGT} = 0.199$). In the case of SXS airline, the lowest source similarity is observed with BBN ($CFRS_{SXS-BBN} = 0.006$). Similarly for BBN, the lowest source overlap is observed with TWI ($CFRS_{BBN-TWI} = 0.006$). Finally, in terms of MGA, the highest source similarity is observed with THY ($CFRS_{MGA-THY} = 0.512$), while the lowest similarity is observed with BBN ($CFRS_{MGA-BBN} = 0.009$).

For the year 2024, when the resource similarities between airline operators are compared in the context of Direct Fleet (DF) information and Cluster Fleet (CF) information, it is seen that a total of 56 competitor pairs are competitors in terms of resource similarity in the analysis made with DF, while this number increases to 76 in the CF table where similar aircraft are grouped. When the competitor pairs are analyzed individually in terms of resource similarity, it is seen that the resource similarity values of 44 competitor pairs increased in the analysis with CF, while this number decreased in 32 competitor pairs.

An overall assessment for all years shows that the amount of overlap in terms of firms' resources increases when the type of analysis is changed in all of the years in question. In addition, both DF and CF analyses reveal that there is an asymmetry between airline pairs in all years in question. These asymmetries suggest that small firms are more similar to the resources of large firms, while large firms do not share this similarity to the same extent. This suggests that small firms may be more affected by the strategic moves of large firms.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the fleet structures of airline companies operating in Turkey in the years 2022-2024 were analyzed and resource similarity analyses were performed based on these data. An increase in the total number of aircraft was observed every year; the total number of aircraft increased from 565 in 2022 to 634 in 2023 and 679 in 2024. This increase was mainly driven by the fleet expansion of Turkish Airlines (THY), Pegasus, SunExpress and BBN. THY had the largest fleet in all three years, while Air Anka usually had the fewest aircraft. THY's variety of aircraft and large fleet made it the airline with the highest source similarity to other airlines.

Source similarity analyses were conducted using two different methods. Direct Fleet (DF) and Cluster Fleet (CF). In the DF analysis, aircraft are considered only by their own make and model, while in the CF analysis, aircraft are grouped according to range, seat capacity and fuselage type. Thanks to the CF approach, source

similarity between more competitor pairs was identified. In this context, while 54 competitor pairs had similar resources in the DF analysis in 2023, this number increased to 76 in the CF analysis. This shows that the analyses conducted by grouping the aircraft reveal similarities more clearly and comprehensively. In this respect, it is considered that the main question that the research seeks to answer has been answered. In other words, the fact that source similarity analyses are conducted with different methods constitutes an important difference. This difference was not analyzed with statistical methods, but the findings show that competitor pair overlap has increased significantly.

The similarity ratios obtained not only revealed competitive relationships, but also provided important operational information. This is because airlines with similar aircraft types (e.g. in terms of range and seat capacity) may require similar maintenance schedules, common spare parts and pilots trained for the same type of aircraft. Therefore, it can be said that companies with similar fleet structures may experience overlaps not only in terms of aircraft types but also in areas such as fleet management, technical infrastructure and human resource planning. In this sense, grouped analyses can not only measure similarity but also provide clues about cooperation in terms of various factors.

The research has various theoretical and practical contributions. Competition among airlines is affected not only by the markets they serve but also by the similarity of the resources they utilize. In this context, it can be argued that similar fleet structures cause firms to be more cautious in responding to competitors when they make a move. This supports the resource-based view and suggests that firms should consider resource similarity in their competitor analysis. Small firms may be under more strategic pressure than large firms due to their limited resources, which is important to consider in practice. Newly established airlines may be encouraged to create different fleet structures than larger firms. This would provide diversity in terms of resources and prevent small firms from having difficulty in competing with large firms.

This study has some limitations. First of all, the data used were obtained entirely from secondary sources, namely the annual reports of the Directorate General of Civil Aviation. Since these reports are summarized information prepared for external observation, they may not fully reflect firms' internal strategic decisions, fleet utilization flexibility or operational differences. This limits the scope of the analysis. Furthermore, resource similarity is analyzed through comparative ratios and matrix interpretations rather than statistical tests. This approach does not reduce the accuracy of the findings, but it makes it difficult to establish cause and effect relationships and may cause some inferences to remain at the observational level only. The study covers only the years 2022, 2023 and 2024 and does not include time analysis to reveal long-term trends. Therefore, it is not possible to observe how airlines develop strategic orientations over time.

In this study, resource similarities among airlines are analyzed by grouping fleet structures. The effects of these similarities on competitive behavior and financial performance are not addressed. In future research, the direct and indirect effects of these similarities on competitive behavior can be examined and research on this issue can be deepened. In particular, it can be analyzed whether firms with high resource similarity have similar profitability ratios or operational costs.

The research covers a time period of 3 years. A trend analysis to be conducted in this direction by extending the year range in future research can give a general trend about the direction of the degree of similarity of resources in the airline industry. On the other hand, in addition to the aircraft used in future research, the similarity of different types of resources such as slot rights, flight networks, human resources or maintenance infrastructure can also be included in the research. Thus, the concept of resource similarity can be addressed in a multidimensional manner.

Finally, since this analysis only covers airline companies in Turkey, similar studies can be conducted for companies in different countries to make comparative analyses. International comparisons provide the opportunity to assess the competitive position and strategic similarities of Turkish airlines in a broader framework. In addition, in the future, machine learning and artificial intelligence analyses can be developed using this data.

Conflicts of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in the writing of this article.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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